

HOW TO BEGIN ANCESTRAL VENERATION

English

HOW TO BEGIN ANCESTRAL VENERATION

“
A Universal
First Step For
The Eue Nation
”

~ TŌGBENLŌ AMLIMA MAWUVI

Master Of The Return,
Voice Of The Ancestors Echoing Eternity!

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Connect via our platforms for language revival and the revolution work.
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Introduction

In our last teaching titled, “*Libations & Ancestral Venerations: the Forgotten Backbone of Ewe Spirituality*”, we reminded ourselves of a truth most of our people already feel deep in their bones: **our ancestors are not dead — they are waiting.**

But after that article, many asked: “*How do we start? What if I have never done this before? Must I wait for a diviner before greeting my own ancestors?*”

The answer is simple: **NO**. Every child of the soil has the right — and duty — to bow to the ones who walked before. Consultation may later give special directions, but you do not need to wait for anyone before taking the first step.

This guide is that first step. It is simple, universal, and accessible to anyone who desires to reconnect.

🙄 Why Begin Now?

“Without roots, the tree withers. Without ancestors, the living scatter”

Ancestors are the roots of our tree. If we never water them, our branches wither.

Without ancestral remembrance, the Ewe nation loses its spiritual backbone.

Each personal reconnection strengthens the collective, until our land once again walks in its full destiny.

🔥 The Basic Universal First-Step Ritual

This is the minimum doorway for beginners. No complex requirements, no fear. Just sincerity.

Items Needed 📄

1. Clean water (in a calabash/bowl) – life, cooling, cleansing.
2. Alligator pepper (optional, for opening the way).
3. White cloth (optional, for purity and humility).

Steps 📌

1. Find a quiet place: the family compound, under a tree, or even your yard if you cannot yet reach your hometown.
2. Spread the white cloth (or stand barefoot if no white cloth).
3. Hold the calabash of water. Lift it towards the sky, then pour slowly onto the earth.
4. Speak clearly:

English:

“Ancestors of my blood, I greet you. I am [name], child of [father/mother’s name]. Forgive my silence. Today I remember you. Walk with me, guide me, and protect me.”

Adagana/Eue (simple form):

“Miawoe dzɔ, miawoe na ame. Nye [name], vi ɖe [father/mother’s name]. Taflatse be mele miafe ŋkɔ dzi. Mia na kpɔ dzɔdzɔ kple nya me.”

5. If you have alligator pepper: chew one seed, spray lightly onto the ground.
6. Bow your head or kneel in silence.

That’s it. The ancestors now recognize you. The door is opened.

After the First Step

Once you have begun, keep the connection alive. You may:

- ✓ Pour water weekly or monthly.
- ✓ Call their names when you need strength.
- ✓ Visit your hometown when possible for deeper rituals.

If challenges persist, then seek consultation for more specific directions.

Closing Call

This is how we begin. Simple, honest, and powerful. The ancestors are not waiting for perfection — they are waiting for remembrance.

The time has come for every son and daughter of the Eue land to bow, pour water, and speak truth. When we reconnect individually, we rise collectively.

Ɖe mia dzo! Let us rise!

Regards,

Tɔgbɛŋlɔ Amlima Mawuvi

*Master of Return,
Voice of the ancestors echoing eternity!*

👍 Author's Note

**“Without roots, the tree wither.
Without ancestors, the living scatter”**

#BeAfrikanNow #AZUMEGBE

♻️ **This is the Code:** share it! Be part of the reset!

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